

Synthesis of Some 2-Furyl and 2-Thienyl Chromones**

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III (a-f); X=H
IV (a-f); X=OH
V (a-f); X=O.Ac

VII (a-f)

a: R₁=CH₃; R₂=Br; R₃=2-furyl;
b: R₁=Br; R₂=CH₃; R₃=2-furyl;
c: R₁=Br; R₂=Cl; R₃=2-furyl;
d: R₁=Br; R₂=Cl; R₃=2-thienyl;
e: R₁=Br; R₂=CH₃; R₃=2-thienyl;
f: R₁=CH₃; R₂=Br; R₃=2-thienyl.

IN continuation of our investigations¹ on chromones, we report here, the synthesis of some 2-(2'-furyl) and 2-(2'-thienyl) chromones. These chromones have been obtained by two routes. In the first scheme, the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (Ia-f) were condensed under basic conditions with the furan-2-aldehyde or thiophene-2-aldehyde, to give the corresponding chalcones (IIa-f). While the yields in the former ranged from 45 to 65%, the latter give yields between 70-90% under similar conditions. Oxidative ring closure of these chalcones with SeO₂ afforded the chromones(IIIa-f)²⁻⁴.

Treatment of the chalcones with hydrogen peroxide under Algar-Flynn-Oyamada reaction^{5,6} conditions gave the 3-hydroxy derivative of the chromones(IVa-f), the ir spectra of which show the hydroxyl band in the region of 3250 cm⁻¹. The shift to lower frequencies indicate some degree of chelation of the hydroxyl group⁷.

Alternatively, the chromones were prepared by cyclodehydration (in acidic medium) of the corresponding-β-diketones (VIIa-f) which, in turn were obtained from the corresponding esters(VIa-f)^{8,9} by Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement. These chromones were identical with those obtained by the first route (m.p. and m.m.p.). All the chromones analysed correctly for C and H and showed the ir peaks in the expected regions. The pmr spectra of all the chromones (*vide* experimental) confirm the structures. The exact position of the peaks have been assigned by decoupling experiments.

I (a-f); Y=H
VI (a-f); Y=CO.R₃

II (a-f)

Experimental

All m.p.s are uncorrected

Preparation of Chalcones :

A mixture of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.002 mole) and freshly distilled furfuraldehyde or thiophene-2-aldehyde (0.0025 mole) dissolved in ethanol or methanol (20-25 ml) was treated in the cold with KOH (40%, 2.5 ml) with stirring. After 3 hrs the mixture was poured into HCl (1 : 1) containing crushed ice. The filtered solid was washed with water and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. M.p.s and yields were as under :

IIa, 124-26°, 66% ; IIb, 86-87°, 60% ;
IIc 143-45°, 45% ; IId, 168-69°, 77% ;
IIe, 129-30°, 90% ; II f, 133-34°, 72%.

Preparation of Chromones from Chalcones :

(a) From Furylchalcones :

A mixture of chalcone (0.005 mole), freshly sublimed SeO₂ (1 g) and dry amyl alcohol (25 ml) was refluxed (oil bath ; 160-70°) for 20 hrs, cooled and filtered to remove selenium. The filtrate was repeatedly washed with NaOH solution (2%) and water. Removal of the amyl alcohol by steam distillation gave the chromone, which was purified by recrystallisation.

(b) From Thienylchalcones :

A chalcone (0.001 mole) was similarly refluxed in amylalcohol for 24-26 hrs with SeO₂ (0.5 g). The solid obtained after filtration was washed with NaOH solution (2%) and water to remove unconverted chalcone. Extraction with solvent, filtration and recrystallisation gave desired product.

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The thienyl chromones were sparingly soluble in cold amyl alcohol and hence, the process was modified as described. M.p.s, yields and solvents of crystallisation are given below :

- IIIa, 202-03°, 60%, ethanol ;
 IIIb, 192-93°, 65%, ethanol ;
 IIIc, 194-95°, 50%, ethanol ;
 IIId, 180-81°, 50%, ethanol ;
 IIIe, 197-98°, 75%, ethanol ;
 IIIf, 222-23°, 55%, acetic acid.

Preparation of 3-Hydroxychromones :

To a well cooled solution of a chalcones (0.001 mole) in methanol containing NaOH solution (2%, 3 ml), was added with stirring, H₂O₂ (30%, 2.5 ml) in drops and left overnight in a refrigerator. The solid was worked up as usual and recrystallised from acetic acid. The m.p., and yields are as under :

- IVa, 262-63°, 60% ; IVb, 265-66°, 75% ;
 IVc, 269-70°, 78% ; IVd, 245-46°, 55% ;
 IVe, 256-57°, 72% ; IVf, 254-55°, 50%.

Ir Values :

- ν_{max} IVa, 3260, 1610 ; IVb, 3260, 1640 ; IVc, 3260, 1635 ;
 IVd, 3250, 1610 ; IVe, 3260, 1600 ; IVf, 3180, 1605.

Acetylation of 3-Hydroxychromones :

Mere heating of the 3-hydroxychromones with acetic anhydride and cooling gave quantitative yields of the corresponding acetyl derivatives.

- Va, 215-16° ; Vb, 184-85° ; Vc, 214-15° ;
 Vd, 204-05° ; Ve, 182-83° ; Vf, 224-25°.

Preparation of Chromones from- β -Diketones :

The chromones were obtained by the usual procedure¹. The yields were :

- IIIa, 80% ; IIIb, 75% ; IIIc, 70% ;
 IIId, 85% ; IIIe, 92% ; IIIf, 90%.

Usual ir peaks were observed in all the cases.

PMR Data (in δ) ; solvent CDCl₃ :

III(a-c) ; X=O
 III(d-f) ; X=S

CH ₃ protons	a	b	c	d	e	f
IIIa	2.47	7.69	7.90	6.70	7.21	6.60
IIIb	2.51	7.58	8.10	6.69	7.08	6.60
IIIc		7.82	8.09	6.70	7.21	6.60
IIId		7.81	8.07	6.67	7.75	7.16
IIIe	2.44	7.70	7.87	6.68	7.70	7.16
IIIf	2.55	7.5-7.7	8.10	6.66	7.5-7.7	7.16

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Synthesis and Reactions of

p-(Diphenylphosphino)benzoic Acid

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A number of workers^{1,2} have prepared *p*-(diphenylphosphino) benzoic acid (1). In this investigation we wish to report a convenient method for the preparation of (1) and some of its reactions.

We prepared the acid (1) by a one-step oxidation of *p*-tolylidiphenylphosphine, (2) using potassium permanganate, instead of the reported two-step oxidation³. Also, the phosphine (2) was prepared from *p*-tolylidichlorophosphine, *p*-CH₃C₆H₄PCl₂, and phenylmagnesium bromide. The ir spectra